

Basel – Lagerhalle Erlenmatt Ost

Resource assessment of structural components

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Disclaimer: This report is a preliminary resource assessment and should be used as such. The results presented are based on visual inspections and on limited material testing. Material properties and detailed condition of each components should be further assessed prior to any reuse of the components described herein. The authors decline any liability relating to the use of the information given in this report.

Table of content

Summary	5
Zusammenfassung	6
1 Introduction	7
1.1 Lagerhalle Erlenmatt Ost	7
1.2 Lightweight expanded clay aggregate (LECA) concrete panels	8
1.3 Scope and objectives	8
2 Resource assessment results	8
2.1 Preamble	8
2.2 Review of existing data	9
2.2.1 Document list	9
2.2.2 Summary of prior information	9
2.3 On-site visits	9
2.4 Investigations on material properties	10
2.4.1 Localization of the sampling zones	10
2.4.2 Compressive test results	11
2.4.3 Carbonatation and cover concrete thickness measurements	11
2.4.4 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)	11
2.5 Assessment of components	12
2.6 Components factsheets	14
Factsheet ERO01 – Façade LECA Panel	15
Factsheet ERO02 – Cast-in-place slabs	19
Factsheet ERO03 – Cast-in-place walls	22
Factsheet ERO04 – Cast-in-place columns	25
Factsheet ERO05 – Precast stairs	29
3 Conclusion	29
4 References	32
Annex 1 – Location of component types	33
Annex 2 – Facade condition by visual inspection	38
Annex 3 – Material technical examination	40
Annex 4 – Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)	41

Summary

The Lagerhalle Erlenmatt Ost is a 3-story building (basement, ground floor and two upper floors) used for food storage, located in Erlenmatt district in Basel and erected in 1975. Cast-in-place reinforced concrete (RC) slabs, walls, and mushroom columns form the main load-bearing structure of the building. The self-supporting facade is made of lightweight expanded clay aggregate (LECA) concrete panels. The deconstruction of this building is planned, thus making available a large amount of RC components composing the structure and the facades.

Little-known and rarely implemented, the reuse of concrete components from obsolete buildings in new projects is a sustainable approach that promotes a circular economy. When reusing, the components of obsolete buildings are carefully dismantled without being crushed. They are then cleaned, possibly repaired or trimmed, and reassembled with little transformation in a new project, maintaining their shapes and structural properties. In addition to maintaining the embodied energy and history of the reused components, reuse allows the construction industry to reduce demolition waste, greenhouse gas emissions, and material consumption.

This report is a preliminary resource assessment and aims at inventorying and assessing all structural components of the Lagerhalle Erlenmatt Ost, focusing on their potential value for reuse. Interest is mainly in the precast LECA concrete facade panels, but cast-in-place RC components are briefly included. The assessment methodology, detailed in a complementary report, allows identifying all properties needed to evaluate the potential for reuse of a RC component: geometry, material properties, resistance, current condition, accessibility, future durability, aesthetics and environmental impacts. After reviewing available reports and drawings on the building, onsite visits are carried out to complete the information and visually inspect the structural components. During the inspection, the components are assessed with regards to their suitability for reuse and their condition is classified into a five-grade scale.

The building is made up of approximately 4 700 m³ of material constituting the load-bearing system, with approximately 450 m³ of precast LECA concrete and 4 250 m³ of cast-in-place concrete. The LECA panels are damaged and are assessed as **unsuitable for structural reuse**. The other components of the building load-bearing structure are considered in good condition by a first preliminary visual inspection. However, they would require further detailed investigations to gather all data needed to plan a potential future reuse.

The inventoried components are divided into 5 categories: (1) facade components; (2) slab components; (3) wall components; (4) column components; and (5) staircases. For each of these categories a complete factsheet is prepared, including pictures, drawings and useful information on their condition. The volume and weight of each component types are given, as well as their share of the total material volume. The embodied global warming potential (in kgCO_{2eq} and kWh_{oil-eq}) for fabrication and demolition of the components is also calculated.

This document should serve as a base for designing and planning future reuse applications for the concrete components extracted when deconstructing the Lagerhalle Erlenmatt Ost. The information presented here will help planners to prioritize the reuse strategy on the components in the best conditions, with the largest volume share and thus with the largest embodied global warming potential.

Zusammenfassung

Die Lagerhalle Erlenmatt Ost ist ein dreigeschossiges Gebäude (Untergeschoss, Erdgeschoss und zwei Obergeschosse), das für die Lagerung von Lebensmitteln genutzt wird. Es befindet sich im Basler Stadtteil Erlenmatt und wurde 1975 errichtet. Ortbetonplatten, -wände und Pilzstützen bilden das Haupttragwerk des Gebäudes. Die selbsttragende Fassade besteht aus Leichtblähtonplatten (LECA). Der Rückbau dieses Gebäudes ist geplant, so dass eine große Menge an RC-Bauteilen, die die Struktur und die Fassaden bilden, zur Verfügung steht.

Die Wiederverwendung von Betonbauteilen aus veralteten Gebäuden in neuen Projekten ist ein nachhaltiger Ansatz, der die Kreislaufwirtschaft fördert. Bei der Wiederverwendung werden die Bauteile veralteter Gebäude sorgfältig demontiert, ohne sie zu zerkleinern. Anschließend werden sie gereinigt, möglicherweise repariert oder nachbearbeitet und in einem neuen Projekt mit geringen Veränderungen wieder zusammengebaut, wobei ihre Formen, Technologien und mechanischen Eigenschaften erhalten bleiben. Durch die Wiederverwendung bleiben nicht nur die graue Energie und die Geschichte der wiederverwendeten Bauteile erhalten, sondern die Bauindustrie kann auch Abbruchabfälle, Treibhausgasemissionen und den Materialverbrauch reduzieren.

Dieser Bericht ist eine vorläufige Ressourcenbewertung und zielt darauf ab, alle strukturellen Komponenten der Lagerhalle Erlenmatt Ost zu inventarisieren und zu bewerten, wobei der Schwerpunkt auf ihrem potenziellen Wert für die Wiederverwendung liegt. Das Interesse gilt vor allem den vorgefertigten Fassadentafeln aus LECA-Beton, aber auch die ortsfesten RC-Bauteile werden kurz berücksichtigt. Die Bewertungsmethodik, die in einem ergänzenden Bericht detailliert beschrieben wird, ermöglicht es, alle Eigenschaften zu ermitteln, die für die Bewertung des Wiederverwendungspotenzials eines RC-Bauteils erforderlich sind: Geometrie, Materialeigenschaften, Widerstandsfähigkeit, aktueller Zustand, Zugänglichkeit, zukünftige Dauerhaftigkeit, Ästhetik und Umweltauswirkungen. Nach Durchsicht der verfügbaren Berichte und Zeichnungen über das Gebäude werden Vor-Ort-Besuche durchgeführt, um die Informationen zu vervollständigen und die strukturellen Komponenten visuell zu inspizieren. Bei der Inspektion werden die Bauteile hinsichtlich ihrer Eignung für eine Wiederverwendung bewertet und ihr Zustand in eine fünfstufige Skala eingestuft.

Das Gebäude besteht aus ca. 4 700 m³ Material, die das tragende System bilden, davon ca. 450 m³ vorgefertigter LECA-Beton und 4 250 m³ Ortbeton. Die LECA-Platten sind beschädigt und **werden als ungeeignet für eine bauliche Wiederverwendung eingestuft**. Die anderen Komponenten der Tragstruktur des Gebäudes sind nach einer ersten vorläufigen Sichtprüfung in gutem Zustand. Sie bedürfen jedoch weiterer detaillierter Untersuchungen, um alle für die Planung einer möglichen zukünftigen Wiederverwendung erforderlichen Daten zu sammeln.

Die inventarisierten Bauteile sind in 5 Kategorien unterteilt: (1) Fassadenteile, (2) Deckenbauteile, (3) Wandbauteile, (4) Stützenbauteile und (5) Treppenhäuser. Für jede dieser Kategorien wird ein vollständiges Datenblatt mit Bildern, Zeichnungen und nützlichen Informationen über ihren Zustand erstellt. Volumen und Gewicht der einzelnen Bauteiltypen werden ebenso angegeben wie ihr Anteil am gesamten Materialvolumen. Das verkörperte Treibhauspotenzial (in kgCO₂eq und kWh_{oil}-eq) für die Herstellung und den Abriss der Komponenten wird ebenfalls berechnet.

Dieses Dokument soll als Grundlage für die Konzeption und Planung zukünftiger Wiederverwendungsmöglichkeiten für die beim Rückbau der Lagerhalle Erlenmatt Ost gewonnenen Betonteile dienen. Die hier präsentierten Informationen werden den Planern helfen, die Wiederverwendungsstrategie auf die Bauteile mit dem besten Zustand, dem grössten Volumenanteil und damit dem grössten verkörperten Treibhauspotenzial zu konzentrieren.

1 Introduction

1.1 Lagerhalle Erlenmatt Ost

The Lagerhalle Erlenmatt Ost is a building located in Erlenmatt district in Basel (Figure 1), erected in 1975. It was planned by Watterwald + Wenger Architekten. Currently, the building is used by a supplier company for food storage.

The building has a basement, a ground floor, two upper floors and an accessible roof for a total height of 16.70 meter above ground level and occupies a surface area of 25.96 by 110.75 meters. Cast-in-place reinforced concrete (RC) slabs, walls, and mushroom columns form the main load-bearing structure of the building. The self-supporting facade is made of lightweight expanded clay aggregate (LECA) concrete panels.

Figure 1. Lagerhalle Erlenmatt Ost – Localization plan

Longitudinal section

Typical floor plan

Figure 2. Lagerhalle Erlenmatt Ost – Facade of the building, longitudinal section and typical floor plan

The deconstruction of this building is planned, thus making available a large amount of RC components composing the structure and the facades. This document inventories and assesses these components with regards to their potential reuse in a new structure.

1.2 Lightweight expanded clay aggregate (LECA) concrete panels

The LECA concrete used for the self-supporting-facade panels uses expanded clay beads as aggregates to reduce the weight of the components. LECA concrete can thus reach a density between 600 and 1 200 kg/m³ [1] compared to approximately 2 400 kg/m³ for regular concrete mixes. The compressive strength of LECA concrete is between 2.5 and 15 N/mm² [1], also much lower than the compressive strength of a conventional concrete. Another benefit of using expanded clay aggregates is the gains in insulation capabilities. It has been used extensively for self-supporting facade walls and roofing.

Figure 3. LECA concrete granulometry [2], example of use of prefabricated LECA panel [1].

1.3 Scope and objectives

This report aims at inventorying and assessing all structural components of the Lagerhalle Erlenmatt Ost, focusing on their potential value for reuse. The methodology detailed in *“Resource assessment for the reuse of load-bearing reinforced concrete components”* [3], aims at identifying all properties needed to plan the reuse of a component: material properties, resistance, actual condition, aesthetics, accessibility, future durability and environmental impacts. Deconstruction, storage and rehabilitation methods are out-of-scope of this report.

The complete resource assessment of the buildings structural components is presented in chapter 2. The components are divided into 5 categories: (1) facade components; (2) slab components; (3) wall components; (4) column components; and (5) staircases. For each component types of these categories, a complete factsheet is prepared, including pictures, drawings and useful information on their condition. Both precast and cast-in-place RC components are included in the inventory and assessment. These components are part of the load-bearing structure or are self-supporting such as the precast facade components. The following building components are considered as out-of-scope for this report:

- > Non-bearing partitions, doors and windows;
- > HVACS technical equipment;
- > Any electrical equipment;
- > All finishing layers;
- > Furniture.

2 Resource assessment results

2.1 Preamble

The following presents the detailed resource assessment of the concrete structural components of the Lagerhalle Erlenmatt Ost. Results are presented following the methodological steps detailed in the report *“Resource assessment for the reuse of load-bearing reinforced concrete components”* [3].

The assessment focuses primarily on the LECA concrete facade panels. However, as the main cast-in-place RC load-bearing structure represents a significant volume of concrete, a brief description of its components is included. Further detailed investigations would be required to gather all data needed to plan a potential future reuse of these components.

- > Facade component

- > Slab component
- > Wall component
- > Column components
- > Staircases

Each of these categories is subdivided into a certain number of component types, as shown in the figures of Annex 1 – Location of component types. These types are themselves subdivided into subtypes with the same characteristics but slightly varying geometry. All relevant information from the assessment is summarized for each component type in the factsheets given in chapter 2.6.

2.2 Review of existing data

2.2.1 Document list

This report is based on the following documents describing the Lagerhalle Erlenmatt Ost. All other references are given in chapter 4.

Existing plans

- A. Construction plans by Wetterwald + Wenger Architekten, 1973-1974

Existing reports

- B. Building pollutants diagnosis «Schadstoffinventar der Bausubstanz für Rückbau», Joppen & Pita AG, January 2021
- C. Summary of the building pollutants diagnosis «Schadstoffinventar der Bausubstanz für Rückbau», Joppen & Pita AG, January 2021

2.2.2 Summary of prior information

The following summarizes all prior and relevant information found in drawings and reports made available while preparing this report.

Existing plans

The construction drawings from 1973-1974 [A] include only architectural drawings for the various floors of the building, and the facades. Most dimensions of the precast and cast-in-place components are available. Some detailed geometrical information is however missing. As no engineering drawings are made available, there is no information on the rebar layouts (diameter and spacing) and on the connections of the facade panels to the main structure.

Building pollutants diagnoses

Toxicity reports [B and C] indicate the confirmed or suspected presence of asbestos in certain joints adjacent to load-bearing components (window joints, joints between slabs of the staircases, etc.). Before the dismantling for a possible reuse, the joints containing asbestos must be removed and disposed of by a specialized company. The removal should avoid as much as possible the production of dust.

Polychlorinated biphenyls (PCB) was detected in the waterproofing joint sealants used between the facade LECA panels, which is common for buildings built between 1955 and 1975 [4,5]. Contamination with PCBs of the concrete neighboring the joints was checked [B], and found to be negative. During deconstruction, the joint sealant should be completely removed by a specialized company. The removal can be done with a cutter, while avoiding heating the joints or producing dust. Once the joint sealants are completely removed, the panels are free of any pollutants.

Dismantling of all components or overlays containing or with a suspicion of asbestos, PAH or PCB should be done by a specialized company. For any further information or action to be carried out in this regard, please refer to the relevant documents [B].

2.3 On-site visits

A first visit took place on the 12th of April 2022. The weather was sunny and dry. The following people were present:

- > Christina Bronowski, Development Manager, Immobilien Basel-Stadt
- > Mauro Pause, Städtebau & Architektur

- > Jenni Jenisch, Stiftung Habitat
- > Cirillo Mentil, Wenger partner
- > Maléna Bastien Masse, researcher and civil engineer at EPFL, Structural Xploration Lab
- > Julie Devènes, researcher and civil engineer at EPFL, Structural Xploration Lab
- > Nicole Widmer, master student at EPFL

During this visit, the facade panels as well as the main load-bearing structure were rapidly inspected. A first evaluation allowed a rough assessment of their condition and the identification of the required material investigations.

A second visit was made by the EPFL team, authors of this document, on the 15th of June 2022. The weather was again sunny and dry. The location of the samplings for the material investigations on the facade panels is then decided with the material testing laboratory (Basler Baulabor AG). The collection of information on the building is also completed: pictures of building and components, precise assessment of the condition of the facade panels, determination of the color and finishing of each component and visual inspection of the main load-bearing structure. A complementary visit was carried out by the EPFL team on the 27th of September 2022 to gather more photos and inspect the facade panels on a rainy day.

The visual inspections revealed that many of the facade panels have heavy craze cracking as well as some damages on the edges (vertical cracking or concrete chipping). The craze cracking patterns are mostly visible on the South and West facades. On the inside faces of the panels, traces of humidity are visible along the cracks. The main cast-in-place RC structure is however in a very good condition with no noticeable damage.

2.4 Investigations on material properties

Destructive investigations were carried out on the facade panels only.

2.4.1 Localization of the sampling zones

For the Lagerhalle Erlenmatt Ost, 6 sampling zones, localized on Figure 4, are located on different LECA panels, all on level 1 of the building:

- > 3 sampling zones in uncracked components;
- > 3 sampling zones in cracked components;

In all sampling zones, 50-mm-diameter cores were extracted to test the compressive resistance of the LECA concrete and check the carbonation depth. In sampling zones 1 and 4, cores were also extracted to be observed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM).

Figure 4. Localization of sampling zones on floor plan

2.4.2 Compressive test results

The results of the compressive tests on the cores are given in Table 1. The detailed report from the laboratory is given in Annex 3 – Material technical examination.

Only one core per sampling zone is tested. As proposed in the standard SN EN 13791 [6], the result on sample 2 is removed from the analysis because the value clearly stands out when compared to the other results. Using these results, the characteristic value of the concrete compressive strength ($f_{ck,act}$) is obtained.

Results core testing	
Sample 1	8,0 N/mm ²
Sample 2	2,7 N/mm ²
Sample 3	7,8 N/mm ²
Sample 4	8,7 N/mm ²
Sample 5	10,8 N/mm ²
Sample 6	7,4 N/mm ²
f_{cm}	7,98 N/mm²
s	1,35 N/mm ²
$f_{ck,act}$	5,4 N/mm²

Table 1. Results of the compressive tests on cores

Tests to determine the Young's modulus of the LECA concrete could not be conducted because the extracted cores were not long enough. When extracted, Most of them broke at the location of the external layer of reinforcement.

2.4.3 Carbonatation and cover concrete thickness measurements

Due to the high porosity of the LECA concrete, carbonation extends in a non-uniform way over a large depth of the facade panels. It is not possible to clearly fix the depth of carbonation, but it is superior to the cover depth of the rebars in most of the tested zones. This indicates that there is a high risk of corrosion of the rebars which is confirmed by observations during the sampling, as see in Figure 5. The detailed report from the laboratory is given in Annex 3 – Material technical examination.

Figure 5. Corroded rebar

2.4.4 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

The LECA concrete was assessed by SEM. The detailed report from the laboratory is given in Annex 4 – Scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The scan showed the high porosity of the concrete, with pore diameters reaching 10 mm. It also confirmed that the depth of carbonation is larger than 30 mm. There is little or no presence of silica gel, which would indicate an active alkali-silica reaction in the concrete, leading to

its premature deterioration. Shrinkage cracks are however visible, perpendicular to the surface and up to a depth of 27 mm. This confirms the visual inspections and other material investigations.

2.5 Assessment of components

The LECA panels are damaged and are assessed as **unsuitable for structural reuse**. This also includes any self-supporting applications, such as reuse as facade components or partitioning walls. The damages observed on most components are heavy cracking (as seen in Figure 6) and carbonation of the cover concrete. Moreover, the LECA concrete has a high porosity and a very low compressive strength. The panels are exposed to rain, and because of the cracking and high porosity of the concrete, humidity has reached the rebars which are now most likely corroded. This is confirmed by the observation made during sampling for material testing (Figure 5) as well as the presence of vertical longitudinal cracks on the edges of the panels (3rd image in Figure 6). These vertical cracks could be due to the swelling of corroded steel. Nevertheless, the material is available and could be reused in a downcycling process or recycled. The existing rebars should be removed or protected from water to prevent further corrosion, after verifying that the humidity content in the panels is low enough.

The detailed condition assessment through visual inspection of the facades is given in the figures of Annex 2 – Facade condition by visual inspection. Panels located on 1st floor were inspected both from the inside and the outside. The worst grade, between the inside and outside observation, is kept. Panels located on the 2nd floor were inspected only from the outside using binoculars, which may partly explain their better grading. Due to the results of the material investigations carried out on the LECA concrete and the expected corrosion of the rebars due to cracking, high porosity and carbonatation of the cover concrete, the grades given during visual inspection are reduced by one level to obtain the final evaluation of the condition of the components.

The components are listed in the following tables. Any openings for pipes in the components are ignored at this stage and only the perimeter dimensions are given.

Figure 6. Cracked and damaged LECA panels

Category	Material	Type N°	Component type	Condition	Component subtype	Component dimensions	Quantity	Area	Volume	LECA Significance*	Total Significance**
Facade components	LECA RC	01	facade panel		1 – Long facade, main panel	2500 x 4700 x 180	80 u	940 m ²	169 m ³	39 %	3.6 %
					2 – Long facade, main panel	2600 x 4700 x 180	72 u	880 m ²	158 m ³	36.5 %	3.4 %
					3 – Long facade, corner panel	2980 x 4700 x 180	8 u	112 m ²	20,2 m ³	4.5%	0.4 %
					4 – Short facade, main panel	3150 x 4700 x 180	32 u	474 m ²	85,3 m ³	20 %	1.8 %
Slabs	Cast-in-place RC	02	Cast-in-place slabs		Slab over basement	L x l x 420 mm	2562 m ²	-	1076 m ³	-	23.0 %
					Slab over 1 st floor and ground floor	L x l x 380 mm	5123 m ²	-	1947 m ³	-	41.6 %
					Slab over 2 nd floor (roof slab)	L x l x 250 mm	5262 m ²	-	640 m ³	-	13.7 %
Walls	Cast-in-place RC	03	Cast-in-place walls		Basement + ground floor – walls 20 cm	4800 x L x 200	82 m ²	-	16.3 m ³	-	0.3 %
					Basement + ground floor – walls 25 cm	4800 x L x 250	397 m ²	-	99.4 m ³	-	2.1 %
					1 st floor – walls 20 cm	4600 x L x 200	39 m ²	-	7.82 m ³	-	0.2 %
					1 st floor – walls 25 cm	4600 x L x 250	190 m ²	-	47.6 m ³	-	1.0 %
					2 nd floor – walls 20 cm	4400 x L x 200	37 m ²	-	7.48 m ³	-	0.2 %
					2 nd floor walls 25 cm	4400 x L x 250	182 m ²	-	45.5 m ³	-	1.0 %
Columns	Cast-in-place RC	04	Cast-in-place columns (with mushroom head)		Basement floor – mushroom column	3700 x 1100 x 700 mm + mushroom	12 u	-	66,9 m ³	-	1.4 %
					Basement floor – simple column	4200 x 1100 x 700 mm	2 u	-	6,5 m ³	-	0.1 %
					Ground floor – mushroom column	3850 x 900 x 600 mm + mushroom	12 u	-	60,3 m ³	-	1.3 %
					Ground floor – simple column	4400 x 900 x 600 mm	2 u	-	4,8 m ³	-	0.1 %
					1 st and 2 nd floor – central mushroom column	3650 x 700 x 540 mm + mushroom	24 u	-	96,7 m ³	-	2.1 %
					1 st and 2 nd floor – side mushroom column	3650 x 700 x 390 mm + mushroom	44 u	-	107,8 m ³	-	2.3 %
					1 st and 2 nd floor – corner mushroom column	3650 x 700 x 390 mm + mushroom	8 u	-	13,8 m ³	-	0.3 %
					1 st and 2 nd floor – simple column	4150 x 700 x 540 mm	4 u	-	6,3 m ³	-	0.1 %
Stairs	Precast RC	05	Precast stairs		Stair	n.a	20 u	-	-	-	-

* Significance calculated for the LECA panels only (considered volume = total volume of LECA panels)

** total volume excluding stairs

Table 2. Summary table of the LECA panels, slabs, walls, columns and stairs

2.6 Components factsheets

The following pages contain the factsheets of every selected component type.

- > Factsheet ERO01 - Facade LECA panel
- > Factsheet ERO02 – Cast-in-place slabs
- > Factsheet ERO03 – Cast-in-place walls (staircase walls)
- > Factsheet ERO04 – Cast-in-place columns
- > Factsheet EROE05 – Precast stairs

Type ERO01

Category: Facade elements

Facade LECA Panel

Location

Long facade

Short facade

- Subtype 1
- Subtype 2
- Subtype 3
- Subtype 4

Facade LECA panel

Outdoor view

Cracking pattern

Concrete sample

Color and finishing

Type ERO01

Category: Facade elements

Facade LECA Panel

Connection

Subtype n° 1, dimensions

1:100

Subtype n°1, cross-section

1:20

Type ERO01

Category: Facade elements

Facade LECA Panel

Description

Construction year	1973
Material	Light weight concrete made with expanded clay aggregates and steel reinforcement
Actual location	All 4 facades of the building
Initial function	Facade self-supporting element
Accessibility	Easy – No further demolition required before
Anchor points	None
Exposition	Outdoor, exposed to rain and water flow
Color	Shades of grey, closest RAL 702
Finishing	Exposed concrete, multiple cracks
Overlays	Type Fixation Thickness
	None - -
Connexion type	4 connecting point to the slabs with bolted angle iron
Deconstruction tool	Unscrewer

Condition and durability

Condition assessment	16% Acceptable
	57% Deviant
	20% Bad
	7% Failure
Carbonatation depth [mm]	> 30 mm
Toxic substance	PCB in joints

Mechanical characteristics

Concrete density (ρ_c)	1'145 kg/m ³
Concrete compressive strength (f_{ck})	5.4 N/mm ²
Concrete young modulus (E_{cm})	n.a.
Reinforcement tensile strength (f_{sk})	n.a.
Reinforcement young modulus (E_s)	n.a.

Element	Geometry			Inventory						Environmental impacts			
	Subtype	Dimensions (W x L x T) [mm]	Reinforcement [mm]	Cross-section resistance [kNm]	Quantity [u]	Weight [kg/u]	Total area [m ²]	Total volume [m ³]	LECA Significance	Total Significance	Initial production		Conventional demolition
[kgCO ₂ -eq/u]												[kWh oil-eq/u]	
1	2500 x 4700 x 180	V: Ø 4; S = 7 cm H: Ø 4; S = 30 cm	-	80	2463	940	169	39%	3.6 %	1069	32	3501	130
2	2600 x 4700 x 180	V: Ø 4; S = 7 cm H: Ø 4; S = 30 cm	-	72	2561	880	158	36.5%	3.4 %	1111	33.3	3660	136
3	2980 x 4700 x 180	V: Ø 4; S = 7 cm H: Ø 4; S = 30 cm	-	8	2935	112	20.2	4.5 %	0.4 %	1274	38.1	4195	155
4	3150 x 4700 x 180	V: Ø 4; S = 7 cm H: Ø 4; S = 30 cm	-	32	3103	474	85.3	20 %	1.8 %	1347	40.3	4435	164

V = vertical; H = horizontal

Type ERO01

Category : Facade elements

Facade LECA Panel

Additional information

Additional note	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > The panels are damaged and unsuitable for reuse as structural elements. This also includes any self-supporting applications, such as a reuse as façade elements or partitioning walls. The damages observed on most elements are heavy cracking and carbonation of the cover concrete. Moreover, the LECA concrete has a high porosity and a very low compressive strength. The panels are exposed to rain, and because of the cracking and high porosity of the concrete, humidity has reached the rebars which are now most likely corroded. This is confirmed by the observation made during sampling for material testing and the vertical cracks located on the edges of some panels. These vertical crack can be due to the swelling of corroded steel. > The embodied global warming potential (in kgCO₂eq) and the grey energy (in kWh oil-eq) for fabrication and demolition of the elements is calculated using their weight and the equivalent factors available in the Life Cycle Assessment KBOB database. The considered factors are the following: (1) Lightweight concrete stone: expanded clay – KBOB ID-Number 02.004, (3) Reinforcement steel – KBOB ID-Number 06.003.
Attention point	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > The waterproofing joints sealant placed between the facade elements contain polychlorinated biphenyls (PCB). However, measurements have shown that the concrete neighboring the joints is not contaminated. The panels and its material can be reused once the joints have been properly and completely removed by a specialized company. The removal can be done with a cutter, while avoiding heating the joints or producing dust.

Type ERO02

Category: Slab

Cast-in-place slabs

Location

Cast-in-place slabs

Color and finishing

Type ERO02

Category: Slab

Cast-in-place slabs

Description

Construction year	1973
Material	Cast-in-place reinforced concrete
Actual location	All floors
Initial function	Slab load-bearing element
Accessibility	Difficult – three & more elements to dismantle before
Anchor points	None
Exposition	Inside, not exposed
Color	Shades of grey, closest RAL 7044
Finishing	Marks of the wooden formwork boards
Overlays	Type Fixation Thickness
	Unknown, the presence of a screed should be verified by drilling a core.
Connexion type	Monolithic connexions between slabs,walls and columns
Deconstruction tool	Diamond saw and hydro-blasting

Condition and durability

Condition assessment	100 % Good
Carbonatation depth [mm]	n.a
Toxic substance	None

Mechanical characteristics

Density	2 500 kg/m ³ (estimate)
Concrete compressive strength	n.a
Concrete young modulus	n.a
Reinforcement tensile strength	n.a
Reinforcement young modulus	n.a

Element	Geometry			Inventory				Environmental impacts			
	Dimensions (W x L x T) [mm]	Reinforcement [mm]	Cross-section resistance [kNm]	Quantity [m ²]	Weight [kg/ m ²]	Total volume [m ³]	Total Significance	Initial production [kgCO ₂ -eq/m ²]	Conventional demolition	Initial production [kWh oil-eq/m ²]	Conventional demolition
Over basement	W x L x 420	n.a	-	2562	1050	1076	23 %	93.5	13.7	129	55
Over ground and 1 st floor	W x L x 380	n.a	-	5124	950	1947	41.6 %	84.6	12.3	117	49
Over 2 nd floor (roof floor)	W x L x 250	n.a	-	2562	625	640	13.7 %	55.6	8.1	77	33

Type ERO02

Category: Slab

Cast-in-place slabs

Additional information

Additional note

- > The embodied global warming potential (in kgCO₂eq) and the grey energy (in kWh oil-eq) for fabrication and demolition of the elements are calculated using the weight and the equivalent factors available in the Life Cycle Assessment KBOB database. The considered factors are the following: Concrete for buildings (without reinforcement) - KBOB ID-Number 01.002
- > Since the reinforcement layout of the slabs is not available, the environmental impact is calculated by considering only the weight of the cast-in-place RC, with a higher density than plain concrete. The impacts are obtained using only factors for concrete production. The exact impacts of the steel production are thus neglected, and the results may be underestimated.

Attention point

- > A detailed inspection and investigation have not been carried out on these elements. The data should therefore be treated with caution and should be verified and investigated further in case of reuse of the elements.
-

Type ERO03

Category: Wall

Cast-in-place walls (staircase walls)

Location

Cast-in-place walls

Color and finishing

Type ERO03

Category: Wall

Cast-in-place walls (staircase walls)

Description				Condition and durability	
Construction year	1973			Condition assessment	100% Good
Material	Cast-in-place reinforced concrete			Carbonatation depth [mm]	n.a
Actual location	All floor			Toxic substance	None
Initial function	Wall load-bearing element			Mechanical characteristics	
Accessibility	Difficult – three & more elements to dismantle before			Density (ρ_c)	2 500 kg/m ³ (estimate)
Anchor points	None			Concrete compressive strength (f_{ck})	n.a
Exposition	Inside, not exposed			Concrete young modulus (E_{cm})	n.a
Color	Shades of grey, closest RAL 7044			Reinforcement tensile strength (f_{sk})	n.a
Finishing	Marks of the wooden formwork boards			Reinforcement young modulus (E_s)	n.a
Overlays	Type	Fixation	Thickness		
	None	-	-		
Connexion type	Monolithic connexions with slabs				
Deconstruction tool	Diamond saw and hydro-blasting				

Element	Geometry			Inventory				Environmental impacts			
	Dimensions (H x L x T) [mm]	Reinforcement [mm]	Cross-section resistance [kNm]	Quantity [m ²]	Weight [kg/u m ²]	Total volume [m ³]	Total Significance	Initial production [kgCO ₂ -eq/m ²]	Conventional demolition	Initial production [kWh oil-eq/m ²]	Conventional demolition
Basement + ground floor	4800 x L x 200	n.a	-	82	500	16.3	0.3 %	45	7	62	26
	4800 x L x 250	n.a	-	397	625	99.4	2.2 %	56	8	77	33
1 st floor	4600 x L x 200	n.a	-	39	500	7.82	0.2 %	45	7	62	26
	4600 x L x 250	n.a	-	190	625	47.6	1.0 %	56	8	77	33
2 nd floor	4400 x L x 200	n.a	-	37	500	7.48	0.2 %	45	7	62	26
	4400 x L x 250	n.a	-	182	625	45.5	1.0 %	56	8	77	33

Type ERO03

Category: Wall

Cast-in-place walls (staircase walls)

Additional information

Additional note	<ul style="list-style-type: none">> The embodied global warming potential (in kgCO₂eq) and the grey energy (in kWh oil-eq) for fabrication and demolition of the elements is calculated using their weight and the equivalent factors available in the Life Cycle Assessment KBOB database. The considered factors are the following: Concrete for buildings (without reinforcement) - KBOB ID-Number 01.002> Since the reinforcement layout of the walls is not available, the environmental impact is calculated by considering only the weight of the cast-in-place RC, with a higher density than plain concrete. The impacts are obtained using only factors for concrete production. The exact impacts of the steel production are thus neglected, and the results may be underestimated.
Attention point	<ul style="list-style-type: none">> A detailed inspection and investigation have not been carried out on these elements. The data should therefore be treated with caution and should be verified and investigated further in case of reuse of the elements.

Type ERO04

Category: Column

Cast-in-place columns

Location – 1st and 2nd floor columns

1st and 2nd floor: ■ Central mushroom column ■ Side mushroom column ■ Corner mushroom column ■ Simple column

Cast-in-place columns

Color and finishing

Type ERO04

Category: Column

Cast-in-place columns

1st and 2nd floor - central mushroom, dimensions

1:50

Type ERO04

Category: Column

Cast-in-place columns

Description				Condition and durability		
Construction year	1973			Condition assessment	100% Good	
Material	Cast-in-place reinforced concrete			Carbonatation depth [mm]	n.a	
Actual location	All floors			Toxic substance	None	
Initial function	Column load-bearing element			Mechanical characteristics		
Accessibility	Difficult – three & more elements to dismantle before			Density (ρ_c)	2 500 kg/m ³ (estimate)	
Anchor points	None			Concrete compressive strength (f_{ck})	n.a	
Exposition	Inside, not exposed			Concrete young modulus (E_{cm})	n.a	
Color	Shades of grey, closest RAL 7044			Reinforcement tensile strength (f_{sk})	n.a	
Finishing	Marks of the wooden formwork boards			Reinforcement young modulus (E_s)	n.a	
Overlays	Type	Fixation	Thickness			
	None	-	-			
Connexion type	Monolithic connexions with slabs					
Deconstruction tool	Diamond saw or hydro-blasting					

Element	Geometry			Inventory				Environmental impacts					
	Dimensions (H x L x T) [mm]	Reinforcement [mm]	Cross-section resistance [kNm]	Quantity [u]	Weight [t/u]	Total volume [m ³]	Total Significance	Initial production	Conventional demolition	Dismantling by sawing	Initial production	Conventional demolition	Dismantling by sawing
Subtype								[kgCO ₂ -eq/u]			[kWh oil-eq/u]		
Basement floor, mushroom	3700 x 1100 x 700	n.a	-	12	13.9	66.9	1.4 %	1240	181	1.6	1714	724	98.3
Basement floor, simple	4200 x 1100 x 700	n.a	-	2	8.1	6.5	0.1 %	720	105	0.19	994	420	11.9
Ground floor, mushroom	3850 x 900 x 600	n.a	-	12	12.6	60.3	1.3 %	1119	163	1.54	1546	654	96.6
Ground floor, simple	4400 x 900 x 700	n.a	-	2	5.9	4.8	0.1 %	529	77	0.13	731	309	8.3
1 st and 2 nd floor, central mushroom	3650 x 700 x 540	n.a	-	24	10.1	96.7	2.1 %	896	131	1.52	1239	524	95.3
1 st and 2 nd floor, side mushroom	3650 x 700 x 390	n.a	-	44	6.1	107.8	2.3 %	545	80	0.85	754	319	52.9
1 st and 2 nd floor, corner mushroom	3650 x 700 x 390	n.a	-	8	4.3	13.8	0.3 %	384	56	0.54	530	224	33.6
1 st and 2 nd floor, simple column	4150 x 700 x 540	n.a	-	4	3.9	6.3	0.1 %	349	51	0.09	482	204	5.8

Type ERO04

Category: Column

Cast-in-place columns

Additional information

Additional note

- > The embodied global warming potential (in kgCO₂eq) and the grey energy (in kWh oil-eq) for fabrication and demolition of the elements is calculated using their weight and the equivalent factors available in the Life Cycle Assessment KBOB database. The considered factors are the following: Concrete for buildings (without reinforcement) - KBOB ID-Number 01.002
- > Since the reinforcement layout of the columns is not available, the environmental impact is calculated by considering only the weight of the cast-in-place RC, with a higher density than plain concrete. The impacts are obtained using only factors for concrete production. The exact impacts of the steel production are thus neglected, and the results may be underestimated.

Attention point

- > A detailed inspection and investigation have not been carried out on these elements. The data should therefore be treated with caution and should be verified and investigated further in case of reuse of the elements.
-

Type ERO05

Category: Stairs

Precast stairs

Location

Precast stairs

Type ERO05

Category: Stairs

Precast stairs

Description				Condition and durability	
Construction year	1973			Condition assessment	100% Good
Material	Precast reinforced concrete			Carbonatation depth [mm]	n.a
Actual location	All floor			Toxic substance	Asbestos in the joints
Initial function	Stairs load-bearing element			Mechanical characteristics	
Accessibility	Moderate – Some elements should first be removed			Density (ρ_c)	2 500 kg/m ³ (estimate)
Anchor points	None			Concrete compressive strength (f_{ck})	n.a
Exposition	Inside, not exposed			Concrete young modulus (E_{cm})	n.a
Color	Shades of grey, closest RAL 7044			Reinforcement tensile strength (f_{sk})	n.a
Finishing	Exposed concrete with no formwork marks			Reinforcement young modulus (E_s)	n.a
Overlays	Type	Fixation	Thickness		
	None	-	-		
Connexion type	n.a				
Deconstruction tool	To be define according to the connexion type. Most likely diamond saw.				

Element	Geometry			Inventory				Environmental impacts			
	Dimensions (H x L x T) [mm]	Reinforcement [mm]	Cross-section resistance [kNm]	Quantity [u]	Weight [kg/u m ²]	Total volume [m ³]	Significance	Initial production [kgCO ₂ -eq/m ²]	Conventional demolition	Initial production [kWh oil-eq/m ²]	Conventional demolition
Stair	n.a	n.a	-	20	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a

Additional information

Additional note

Attention point	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > The data on the stairs is very scarce. Further investigations is needed in order to get information on their exact geometry, reinforcement layouts, and material properties. > A detailed inspection and investigation have not been carried out on these elements. The data should therefore be treated with caution and should be verified and investigated further in case of reuse of the elements.
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3 Conclusion

This report presents the resource assessment of the precast facade components and cast-in-place load-bearing concrete structure of the Lagerhalle Erlenmatt Ost. The facade LECA panels are damaged and are assessed as **unsuitable for structural reuse**. The other components of the building's load-bearing structure are considered in good condition by a first preliminary visual inspection. However, they would require further detailed investigations to gather all data needed to plan a potential future reuse.

The construction system of the building is made up of repetitive components that can easily be classified into types, facilitating the inventory and the transmission of information through factsheet. This document should serve as a base for designing and planning future reuse applications for the concrete components extracted when deconstructing the Lagerhalle Erlenmatt Ost. The information presented here will help the planners to prioritize the reuse strategy on the components in the best conditions, with the largest volume share and thus with the largest embodied global warming potential.

4 References

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Annex 1 – Location of component types

Figure 7. Location of facade component

Figure 8. Location of slab component

Figure 9. Location of column components

Figure 10. Location of wall components

Figure 11. Location of stairs component

Annex 2 – Facade condition by visual inspection

Figure 12. Visual inspection of the long facade on the highway side and the short facade on the north side

Figure 13. Visual inspection of the long facade on the loading dock side and the short facade on the south side

Annex 3 – Material technical examination

In the next pages, the material test report prepared by BBL is given.

Materialtechnische Untersuchungen, Mauerplatten Fassade, Ziegler
Entnahme von Prüfkörpern aus Fassadenelementen
Version 1.0

Materialtechnische Untersuchung 221228-1

Ziegler AG
Signalstrasse 101
4058 Basel

Version	Änderung	Datum	Freigegeben
1.0	Initial	30.06.2022	MS

I Organisation, Auftrag

Architekt, Planer	EPFL Fribourg Halle Bleue HBL 0-42A Passage du Cardinal 13b, 1700 Fribourg
Projektleiterin	Frau Dr. Maléna Bastien Masse
Auftragnehmer	BBL Basler Baulabor Bauunternehmen der TFB Gruppe Schadstoffe Gartenstrasse 15 CH-4132 Muttenz
Projektleiter	Herr Martin Schäuble Tel.: +41 61 467 70 00 E-Mail: martin.schauble@bbl-lab.ch
Projektleiter Stv.	Herr Devad Kumalic Tel.: +41 61 467 70 00 E-Mail: devad.kumalic@bbl-lab.ch
Auftrag	<p>Um materialtechnische Kenntnisse über die Fassadenplatten (Mauerplatten) zu erlangen, wurde die Basler Balabor AG beauftragt die Kennwerte: Druckfestigkeit, Emodul, Karbonatisierung, AAR Mikroskopie und auch den Bewehrungszustand zu ermitteln.</p> <p>Bei der Entnahme sollten die Platten nicht komplett durchgebohrt werden. Bei den Sackbohrungen konnten keine genügend langen Bohrkerne zur Emodul - Messung entnommen werden.</p> <p>Mittels Radarmessung wurden die Raster der horizontalen und vertikalen Bewehrung festgestellt.</p>
Vorgehensweise	<p>Vor Ort wurden die Platten von Vertretern der EPFL, Frau Maléna Bastien Masse bestimmt. Es sollen drei visuell bessere und an drei schlechteren Platten die Bohrkerne (BK) entnommen werden. Stellen Nr. 1-3 sind an Platten mit visuell gerissenen Oberflächen entnommen worden. An den Stellen Nr. 4-6 wurden an visuell besseren Platten BK entnommen. Jeweils an einer besseren und einer schlechteren Platte (Nr. 1 und Nr. 4) wurden zusätzlich zur Druckfestigkeit und Emodul Prüfkörpern auch jeweils ein BK zur Mikroskopie (AAR) und Karbonatisierung entnommen. Mittels Radar wurde vor der Entnahme die Bewehrung lokalisiert.</p>
Durchführung	15.06.2022
Verteiler	Dieser Bericht wird jeweils dem Auftraggeber und dem Eigentümer der untersuchten Liegenschaft ausgehändigt. Die in diesem Bericht vorhandenen Daten sind vertraulich zu behandeln.

II Übersicht Untersuchungsperimeter

Umfang	Es wurden ausschliesslich Proben im 1.OG entnommen.
Nicht unters. Perimeter	---

1 Fazit - Übersicht der Befunde

Zusammengefasst wurden bei folgenden Platten Proben entnommen

Parzelle

Nr.	Geschoss	Raum	Bauteil	BK Entnahmestellen
1	1. OG	Lager	Wand	BK Stelle 1
2	1. OG	Lager	Wand	BK Stelle 2
3	1. OG	Lager	Wand	BK Stelle 3
4	1. OG	Lager	Wand	BK Stelle 4
5	1. OG	Lager	Wand	BK Stelle 5
6	1. OG	Lager	Wand	BK Stelle 6

2 Fotodokumentation

Lagerhalle Ziegler, 1.OG

Stelle 1

Bauteil Wand

Geschoss 1. OG

Raum Lager

Druckfestigkeit: 8.0 MPa

Rohdichte: 1261 kg/m³

Karbonatisierung: * mm

Bewehrungsraster vertikal: 7 cm

Bewehrungsraster horizontal: 30 cm

Bewehrungs \varnothing vertikal: 4 mm

Bewehrungs \varnothing horizontal: 4mm

KG: KG2-3

Aufnahmedatum: 15.06.2022

Die Karbonatisierung kann nicht genau festgestellt werden, da es viele Hohlräume gibt die durch die Aussenluft zugänglich und somit unregelmässig karbonatisiert sind

Stelle 2

Bauteil Wand

Geschoss 1. OG

Raum Lager

Druckfestigkeit: 2.7 MPa

Rohdichte: 986 kg/m³

Bewehrungsraster vertikal: 7 cm

Bewehrungsraster horizontal: 30 cm

Bewehrungs \varnothing vertikal: 4 mm

Bewehrungs \varnothing horizontal: 4 mm

Aufnahmedatum: 15.06.2022

Stelle 3

Bauteil Wand

Geschoss 1. OG

Raum Lager

Druckfestigkeit: 7.8 MPa

Rohdichte: 1117 kg/m³

Bewehrungsraster vertikal: 7 cm

Bewehrungsraster horizontal: 30 cm

Bewehrungs \varnothing vertikal: 4 mm

Bewehrungs \varnothing horizontal: 4 mm

Aufnahmedatum: 15.06.2022

Stelle 4

Bauteil Wand

Geschoss 1. OG

Raum Lager

Druckfestigkeit: 8.7 MPa

Rohdichte: 1236 kg/m³

Karbonatisierung: *mm

Bewehrungsraster vertikal: 7 cm

Bewehrungsraster horizontal: 30 cm

Bewehrungs \varnothing vertikal: 4 mm

Bewehrungs \varnothing horizontal: 4 mm

KG: KG1

Die Karbonatisierung kann nicht genau festgestellt werden, da es viele Hohlräume gibt die durch die Aussenluft zugänglich und somit unregelmässig karbonatisiert sind.

Aufnahmedatum: 15.06.2022

Stelle 5

Bauteil Wand

Geschoss 1. OG

Raum Lager

Druckfestigkeit: 10.8 MPa

Rohdichte: 1250 kg/m³

Bewehrungsraster vertikal: 7 cm

Bewehrungsraster horizontal: 30 cm

Bewehrungs \varnothing vertikal: 4 mm

Bewehrungs \varnothing horizontal: 4 mm

Aufnahmedatum: 15.06.2022

Stelle 6

Bauteil Wand

Geschoss 1. OG

Raum Lager

Druckfestigkeit: 7.4 MPa

Rohdichte: 1016 kg/m³

Bewehrungsraster vertikal: 30 cm

Bewehrungsraster horizontal: 7 cm

Bewehrungs \varnothing vertikal: 4mm

Bewehrungs \varnothing horizontal: 4 mm

Aufnahmedatum: 15.06.2022

Druckfestigkeit und Rohdichte am Betonbohrkern nach SN EN 12504-1 und 12390-7

Auftrag Nr.: 221228 / Attest 1
 Bauherr: Immobilien Basel-Stadt, Fischmarkt 10, 4001 Basel
 Bauobjekt: **Investigations for Ziegler Lagerhalle and informations for parking LSB**
 Bauteil: **Fassadenplatten Leichtbeton**
 Bauleitung: -
 Unternehmer: -
 Auftraggeber: Immobilien Basel-Stadt, Fischmarkt 10, 4001 Basel , Herr Ruedi Köchlin

Druckpresse:	Presse M1, Typ W+B Walter + Bai, 0 - 3000 kN, Klasse 1 (SN EN 12390-4)		Festigkeit: 1 MPa = 1 N/mm ²
Druckfestigkeitsklasse:	Expositionsklasse:	-	Konsistenzklasse: -
Grösstkorn (geschätzt): 32 mm	mindest Zementgehalt (kg/m ³):	-	Zement: -
Zusatzstoffe II (Filler): -	Mindest LP-Gehalt (Vol-%):	-	max. W/Z Wert: -
Anwendung: -	Zusatzmittel:	-	
Betonhersteller:	Betonsorte/ Rezeptur:	-	
Frischbetonwerte: nicht vorhanden	Verantwortliche Pers. für die Festlegung der Messstellen:		
Probenbezeichnung:	Herstellungsdatum:	Probenzustand:	
Probennahmedatum:	Entnahme	Eingangsdatum:	
Probentransport:	Anzahl Prüflinge:		6
Probenlagerung im Labor bei normalen Raumtemperaturen und Raumluftfeuchtigkeit			

Bohrkerndruckfestigkeit											
Bohrkern-Bezeichnung	Prüfdatum	Probenalter	Masse (g)	Ø (mm)	Länge (mm)	Verhältnis L : Ø	Rohdichte kg/m ³		Höchstlast kN	Druckfestigkeit MPa	
							Einzel	Mittel		Einzel	MW
BK 1	22.06.22		120.35	49.4	49.8	1.01	1261		15.4	8.0	7.6
BK 2	22.06.22		93.56	49.4	49.5	1.00	986		5.1	2.7	
BK 3	22.06.22		105.53	49.4	49.3	1.00	1117	1144	15.0	7.8	
BK 4	22.06.22		117.72	49.4	49.7	1.01	1236		16.6	8.7	
BK 5	22.06.22		118.60	49.4	49.5	1.00	1250		20.7	10.8	
BK 6	22.06.22		95.61	49.4	49.1	0.99	1016		14.2	7.4	

Bewertung der Druckfestigkeit nach SN EN 13791 *											
Standardabweichung Druckfestigkeit (MPa) s											
Standardabweichung Druckfestigkeit (MPa) s (berechnet mit V _k 8%)											
Wert k _n (multipliziert mit k _n wird die jeweils die höhere der beiden Stabw.)											
Mittelwert Druckfestigkeit MW _{CLF}											
Der niedrigere der beiden Werte wird für die Berechnung berücksichtigt:								1.) f _{ck, is} = f _{m(n), is} - k _n · s			
								2.) f _{ck, is} = f _{is, niedrigst} + M			
Charakteristische Druckfestigkeit Bauwerksbeton (f _{ck, is}) Mpa											
EN 12504-1: Festigkeitsvergleich mit der Würfeldruckfestigkeit (Verhältnis Länge zum Durchmesser:1.0)										✓	
Oberflächenbehandlung: Alle Proben beidseitig geschliffen											
Die Messunsicherheit des Messverfahrens kann nach Absprache mit BBL zugestellt werden											
Visuelle Untersuchung der Proben bei Entnahme od. Erhalt/ Allg. Bemerkungen											
Die BK- Druckfestigkeitswerte zeigen eine grosse Streuung. Die Festigkeitswerte können anhand der Rohdichtewerte plausibilisiert werden.											
Der Beton wurde teilweise schlecht verdichtet.											
Ohne schriftliche Genehmigung der Basler Baulabor AG darf der vorliegende Bericht nicht auszugsweise vervielfältigt werden. Die Prüfergebnisse beziehen sich ausschließlich auf die untersuchten Proben /* nicht akkreditierter Bereich											

Annex 4 – Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

In the next pages, the assessment report on the LECA concrete prepared by TFB is given.

Technik und Forschung im Betonbau

Basler Baulabor AG
Herr M. Schäuble
Gartenstrasse 15
4132 Muttenz

Wildegg, 12. Juli 2022

Auftrag Nr. U 221228-01
Mikroskopie im Durchlicht: Ausführliche Gefügeanalyse und Schadenuntersuchung
Versuch TFB Nr. 5480, SOP 3040

Auftraggeber	:	Basler Baulabor AG Gartenstrasse 15 4132 Muttenz
Objekt	:	Ziegler Lagerhalle
Bauteil	:	Wand
Probenart	:	Bohrkerne
Bezeichnung	:	1.M & 4.M
Dünnschliffe	:	221228-01-1M & 221228-01-4M
Untersuchung	:	Durchlicht, natürlich, polarisiert, UV-Auflicht max. Vergrößerung 400/500x
Durchgeführt am	:	11.07.2022
Durchgeführt von	:	JB

TFB AG - Technik und Forschung im Betonbau

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Mikroskopie

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Die Prüfergebnisse haben nur Gültigkeit für die untersuchten Proben. Dieser Bericht darf nicht auszugsweise kopiert werden. Unzerstörte Proben werden nach der Prüfung 2 Monate aufbewahrt. Das Auftragsdossier wird während 13 Jahren archiviert. Der Auftraggeber kann die Dienstleistungen innerhalb von 30 Tagen beanstanden. Bitte beachten Sie die "Allgemeinen Geschäftsbedingungen". Weitere Informationen: www.tfb.ch

Probenbezeichnung	221228-01-1.M	221228-01-4.M
Tiefe	0-30 mm	0-30 mm

Gesteinskörnung

Petrographie und Korngrösse	Liapor: ca. 1-15 mm Sand - hauptsächlich Quarz and Kalkstein: 0-4 mm	
Kornrundung	gerundet und gebrochen	

Bindemittel

Art	Portlandzement	Portlandzement
Hydratationsgrad	hoch	hoch

Poren

Kapillarporosität	homogen verteilt	homogen verteilt
Luftporen	einzelne bis ca. 1 mm Durchmesser	einzelne bis ca. 1 mm Durchmesser
Verdichtungsporen	viele bis ca. 10 mm Durchmesser (ab Tiefe 30 mm in Bohrkern)	viele bis ca. 5 mm Durchmesser (ab Tiefe 30 mm in Bohrkern)

Sekundäre Kristallisationen

Karbonatisierung	10-25 mm von der Oberfläche; max. bis 25 mm entlang Risse	≥30 mm von der Oberfläche
in Poren und Riss	wenig Silikagel in einer Pore	keine

Risse

in der Matrix und durch Liaporkörner	2 Schwindrisse senkrecht zur Oberfläche bis 27 mm Tiefe	2 Schwindrisse senkrecht zur Oberfläche bis 27 mm Tiefe
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Zusammenfassung und Interpretation

Beschreibung Beton-Zusammensetzung und -Gefüge	Der Beton im untersuchten Dünnschliff besteht aus einem Portlandzement und Zuschlagstoffe aus hauptsächlich Liapor und wenig Sand. Die Karbonatisierungstiefe reicht entlang von Schwindrissen bis 25 mm tief.	Der Beton im untersuchten Dünnschliff besteht aus einem Portlandzement und Zuschlagstoffe aus hauptsächlich Liapor und wenig Sand. Die Karbonatisierungstiefe reicht entlang von Schwindrissen über das untere Ende des Dünnschliffs hinaus (>30 mm).
Interpretation	Der Beton im untersuchten Dünnschliff zeigt Schwindrisse senkrecht zu Oberfläche. Es gibt vereinzelte Anzeichen einer Alkali-Aggregat-Reaktion: Silikagel in einer Pore (siehe Abb. 6).	Der Beton im untersuchten Dünnschliff zeigt Schwindrisse senkrecht zu Oberfläche. Es gibt keine Anzeichen für eine Alkali-Aggregat-Reaktion.

Abb. 1: Querschnittbilder der Bohrkerne 1.M (links) und 4.M (rechts).

Abb. 2: Dünnschliff **221228-01-1.M** unter UV-Auflicht. Schwindrisse senkrecht zur Betonoberfläche (rechts) sind mit roten Linien hervorgehoben. Das blaue Rechteck zeigt die Stelle der Abb. 4 und der blaue Kreis zeigt die Stelle von Abb. 6.

Abb. 3: Dünnschliff 221228-01-4.M unter UV-Auflicht. Schwindrisse senkrecht zu Betonoberfläche (rechts) sind mit roten Linien hervorgehoben.

Abb. 4: Dünnschliff 221228-01-1.M in polarisiertem Durchlicht. Die Stelle "A" in Abb. 2 in 25 mm Tiefe von der Oberfläche. Karbonatisierung des Zementsteins (beige) entlang eines Schwindrisses.

Abb. 5: Dünnschliff 221228-01-4.M in polarisiertem Durchlicht. Ein Schwindriss (blau) verläuft von der Betonoberfläche durch ein Liaporkorn (dunkel) hindurch.

Abb. 6: Dünnschliff **221228-01-1.M** in natürlichem Durchlicht. Dünne Ablagerung von Silikagel auf der Wand einer Verdichtungspore. Am unteren Bildrand liegt ein Liaporkorn (dunkel).